

Analysis of Costs and Trends of Antibiotic Consumption at the National Hospital of Obstetrics and Gynecology (NHOG) in 2019-2023

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More Information

How to cite this article: Tuan NH, Mai PQ, Hai NT, Huy PQ, Phuong NN. Analysis of Costs and Trends of Antibiotic Consumption at the National Hospital of Obstetrics and Gynecology (NHOG) in 2019-2023. *Eur J Med Health Res*, 2025;3(3):162-7.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2025.3(3).24

Keywords:

Antibiotics,
cost,
DDD,
National hospital of Obstetric and Gynecology (NHOG).

Abstract

Objective: Analyzing the cost and consumption of antibiotics at National hospital of Obsteric and Gynecology from 2019 to 2023.

Subjects and methods: A cross-sectional descriptive study based on data on antibiotics used in inpatient treatment at the National hospital of Obsteric and Gynecology from 01/01/2019 to 31/12/2023, using cost analysis and DDD analysis methods.

Results: The beta-lactam group accounted for the majority of consumption value (93.7%). Intravenous antibiotics accounted for 91.4% in value. The proportion of original and generic brand-name drug use values was 57.4% and 42.6%. The Department of Obstetric Pathology and department of Obstetric Infections were two departments that used the most antibiotics. The average total DDD/100 bed days of the hospital was 66.2; in which the penicillin and cephalosporin groups had the highest DDD/100 bed days. Antibiotics that need to be managed according to Decision 5631/QD-BYT account for a low proportion of consumption, while meropenem antibiotics tend to increase in consumption ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: The study shows an overall picture of the situation of antibiotic use at National hospital of Obsteric and Gynecology in the 5-year period from 2019 to 2023. It is the basis for proposing that the Drug Treatment Council implement a comprehensive antibiotic management program.

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Introduction

Antibiotics have been the most important medical intervention in the past century, but antibiotic resistance is becoming increasingly serious. In this context, the Ministry of Health issued Decision No. 5631/QD-BYT dated December 31, 2020, emphasizing the importance of antibiotic management programs in hospitals. In particular, synthesizing and analyzing antibiotic use trends based on DDD analysis and ABC analysis is one of the important contents of monitoring and supervising antibiotic use in the antibiotic management program [1].

The National Hospital of Obstetrics and Gynecology (NHOG) is a grade I specialized hospital under the Ministry of Health, a leading facility in the field of obstetrics, family planning and neonatology. The hospital's antibiotic users are mainly special subjects such as pregnant women and newborns. Therefore, monitoring and supervising antibiotic use requires even more attention.

On that basis, to contribute to the effective implementation of antibiotic use monitoring activities in hospitals, the research team applied information technology software in implementing the project with the goal of: Describing the characteristics of antibiotic

use at the Central Maternity Hospital in the period 2019-2023 based on cost analysis and antibiotic consumption trends.

Research Objects and Methods

Research Subjects

Complete data on the list of antibiotics used in inpatient treatment at the National Hospital of Obstetrics and Gynecology (NHOG) from January 1, 2019 to December 31, 2023.

Research Method

Study design: Cross-sectional

Data collection method: Using available documents at the Hospital, the List of antibiotics used, the report on import and export of drugs in inpatient treatment at the National Hospital of Obstetrics and Gynecology (NHOG) for 5 years 2019 - 2023 extracted from the hospital management software (HIS).

Data analysis and processing methods: After extraction and input, the data is cleaned, encoded and processed using Microsoft Excel software, then exported to

Microsoft Power BI software, and the data is visualized using images and charts.

Using the method of calculating the percentage of the number of items and the value of use. The total DDD dose, DDD dose/100 bed days are calculated according to the instructions in Circular 21/2013/TT-BYT dated August 8, 2013. The ATC code and DDD dose of each drug are looked up online on the website of the World Health Organization:

http://www.whooc.no/atc_ddd_index.

Use the Mann-Kendall test to analyze drug consumption trends. The trend is concluded to be increasing if the analysis indexes $S > 0$ and $p < 0.05$, the trend is concluded to be decreasing if $S < 0$ and $p < 0.05$. Cases with analysis results $p > 0.05$ are concluded to have no trend.

Research Results

Structure of Antibiotic Use Value According to Chemical Structure Group

Table 1: Structure of Antibiotic Use Value by Chemical Structure Group

No.	Antibiotic group	Number of active ingredients	Value in use (VND)	Rate of surplus value (%)
1	Penicillin	05	51.113.904.644	63,4
2	Cephalosporin	08	22.398.610.827	27,8
3	Carbapenem	02	2.470.179.644	3,1
4	Lincosamid	01	1.770.971.396	2,2
5	Floroquinolon	01	1.555.443.248	1,9
6	Imidazol	01	1.000.882.117	1,2
7	Sulfonamid	02	212.466.750	0,3
8	Glycopeptid	02	60.193.911	0,1
9	Aminoglycosid	01	19.906.085	0,02
10	Macrolid	01	14.910.120	0,02
	Total	24	80.617.468.741	100,0

The groups of antibiotics used in hospitals are quite diverse, almost all groups of antibiotics used in class I hospitals are available. The beta-lactam group (Penicillin, Cephalosporin, Carbapenem) accounts for the main consumption value, accounting for 94.3% of

the total value of antibiotic use in the hospital. The remaining antibiotic groups account for an insignificant proportion, only less than 3% of the total value of use.

Structure of Antibiotic Use Value According to Some Criteria

Table 2: Structure of Antibiotic Use Value According to Some Criteria

No.	Criteria	Good Till Date (VND)	Ratio (%)
According to route of use			
1	Parenteral Route	73.681.954.330	91,4
2	Oral route	6.935.514.411	8,6
By technical standards group			
1	Generic drugs	34.370.716.909	42,6
2	Innovator drug	46.246.751.832	57,4
According to the management priority level based on the WHO's AWARE classification			
1	Access	40.272.980.336	50,0
2	Watch	25.817.929.350	32,0
3	Other	14.526.559.055	18,0
According to management priority level according to Decision 5631/QD-BYT			

1	Group 1 – Antibiotics that require prioritized management	2.983.113.875	3,7
2	Group 2 – Antibiotics that require monitoring and surveillance of use	1.575.349.333	2,0
3	Consultation not required	76.059.005.533	94,3

The study results showed that injectable and infusion antibiotics accounted for the majority of the total antibiotic use value (91.4%). The value of brand-name antibiotics was higher than that of generic antibiotics, representing 57.4% compared to 42.6%. According to the WHO’s AWARE classification, Access group antibiotics made up half of the total antibiotic use value, while antibiotics in the Watch group accounted for approximately 32%. Based on the classification of antibiotics requiring consultation under Decision No. 5631/QĐ-BYT issued by the Ministry of Health, the hospital's antibiotic use was predominantly in the group that does not require consultation, representing up to 94% of the total value.

Distribution of Antibiotic Use Value Across Hospital Departments

The group of departments with high antibiotic usage value (accounting for more than 80%) includes 6 departments: Pathological Obstetrics Department, General Obstetrics Department, Infectious Obstetrics Department, Anesthesia and Resuscitation Surgery Department, Treatment on Demand Department, and Gynecology and Surgery Department. The remaining departments only account for about 20% of the total antibiotic usage value of the hospital.

Consumption Levels of Antibiotic Groups According to the Number of DDD Doses/100 Bed Days

Table 3: Consumption Levels of Antibiotic Groups According to the Number of DDD Doses/100 Bed Days

No	Antibiotic group	DDD/100 bed days	Ratio (%)
1	Penicillin	33,6	50,7%
2	Cephalosporin	26,0	39,3%
3	Floroquinolon	2,3	3,5%
4	Imidazol	2,0	3,0%
5	Carbapenem	1,1	1,7%
6	Lincosamid	0,9	1,4%
7	Aminoglycosid	0,2	0,3%
8	Macrolid	0,04	0,1%
9	Glycopeptid	0,04	0,1%
10	Sulfonamid	0,04	0,1%
	Total	66,2	100%

During the 5-year period of 2019 - 2023, the Hospital used 10 groups of antibiotics and had an average number of DDD doses/100 bed days of 66.2. Penicillin and Cephalosporin groups were the 2 antibiotic groups most used in the hospital with doses of 33.6 and 26.0 DDD/100 bed days, respectively. Next were Floroquinolone and Imidazole antibiotics, but the number of doses was only about 2 DDD/100 bed days. The remaining antibiotic groups consumed insignificant amounts.

Consumption Trends of Some Antibiotics in the 5-Year Period by Number of DDD/100 Bed Days

The four active ingredients with the highest consumption in the entire hospital include: Ampicillin/sulbactam, amoxicillin/acid clavulanic acid; cefuroxim and cefaclor. The trend analysis results showed that the active ingredient ampicillin/sulbactam

tended to increase over the 5-year period, whereas the number of DDD /100 bed days of cefuroxime tended to decrease. The consumption of antibiotics amoxicillin/acid clavulanic acid and cefaclor did not identify a statistically significant trend.

Some antibiotic active ingredients with low consumption levels of the hospital but belonging to the group of drugs that need to be prioritized for management in group 1 according to Decision 5631/QĐ-BYT include: imipenem/cilastatin, meropenem, vancomycin. The consumption levels of imipenem/cilastatin and vancomycin did not identify a statistically significant increasing/decreasing trend. Meropenem has a statistically significant increasing trend. Notably, Meropenem was not used in 2019, 2020, only used from 2021 and increased from 2022 - 2023 to reach 0.02 DDD/100 bed days.

Figure 1: Consumption Trends of Antibiotics with Large Consumption Volumes

Figure 2: Consumption Trends of Priority Antibiotics

Discussion

The most widely used and most valuable group of antibiotics in the hospital is beta-lactam, accounting for more than 94.6% of the total value of use in the hospital. The beta-lactam group is widely used in hospitals, possibly because this group of drugs has many brands and is diverse in types (route of administration, dosage form, etc.).

The widely used antibiotics are also broad-spectrum antibiotics that are effective against both Gram (-) and Gram (+) bacteria, are resistant to beta-lactamase, and some are effective against P.aeruginosa.

For surgical indications, the recommended first-line antibiotic is a beta-lactam antibiotic combined with a beta-lactamase inhibitor. In addition, beta-lactam antibiotics are also a safe antibiotic group for pregnant

and lactating women, with few unwanted side effects, so they are commonly used in obstetrics.

Intravenous antibiotics account for an overwhelming proportion in terms of both the number of categories and the value of use compared to oral antibiotics (more than 90% of GTSD). This ratio is similar to some studies in hospitals in Vietnam such as Hanoi Obstetrics and Gynecology Hospital (2018) at 89.37%, Thanh Hoa General Hospital (58.8% of items and 81.9% of GTSD), Nghe An Obstetrics and Pediatrics Hospital (72.2% of items, 97.5% of GTSD) [4], [6]. Intravenous antibiotics are of high value because they are commonly used in inpatient treatment for severe infections or patients who are intolerant to oral medications, do not meet treatment requirements, and the unit price of intravenous antibiotics is often many times higher than that of oral antibiotics. Hospitals need to have a

strategy to closely monitor the use of injectable and infusion drugs, and consider switching antibiotics from the intravenous route to the oral route when possible based on clinical assessments according to the guidance in Decision 5631/QD-BYT dated December 31, 2020 of the Ministry of Health.

The ratio of the number of categories and the usage value of antibiotics in the Original Brand Drug group is almost equivalent to that of the Generic group. In 2020 and 2023, the usage value of Original Brand Drug antibiotics was even higher with rates of 66.8% and 69.6%, respectively. This rate is much higher than other hospitals such as the 108 Military Central Hospital, where this rate was only about 15% in 2023, and the Nghe An Maternity and Pediatrics Hospital, where the ratio of Original Brand Drugs was only about 18.8% [2], [4]. This ratio shows that doctors tend to trust using generic drugs more, possibly because generic drugs have the advantage of having gone through a long period of research and testing, so the effectiveness and safety of the drug have been verified and recognized by strict drug management agencies such as FDA, EMA. However, hospitals need to focus on choosing generic drugs to replace original brand drugs to reduce the cost burden on insurance funds, in accordance with treatment trends and economic conditions of the people.

Some priority management categories in group 1 (meropenem, imipenem, vancomycin) and group 2 (amikacin, gentamicin, levofloxacin) according to Decision 5631/QD-BYT only account for a very small value in the cost of antibiotics used (5.7% of GTSD) [1]. This ratio is much lower than other hospitals. At 108 Military Central Hospital, antibiotics that need to be managed (group 1, 2) account for 43.1% and 54.8% respectively in terms of number of items and usage value, while at Kien An Hospital, Hai Phong City, this ratio is 13.5% in terms of value [2], [3]. This is a group of reserve antibiotics, used only in cases of severe infections and other antibiotics are no longer effective. It can be seen that the Central Maternity Hospital has also limited the use of reserve antibiotics, strictly following the consultation and approval process before using these antibiotics.

Departments in the high-use group often treat surgical or internal medicine with associated diseases. Obstetric and gynecological surgeries all require the use of antibiotics before and after surgery to prevent and treat infections. The Obstetric Pathology Department is the department with the highest antibiotic use value in the entire hospital. This is the department with the largest number of beds and patients in the entire hospital. Departments with low utilization value often perform normal delivery, postpartum care, and cancer monitoring and treatment. These subjects mostly stay in the department for a short time, and the amount of

antibiotics used is not much. In addition, these departments, typically the Obstetrics Department, most of the patients can use oral antibiotics instead of injectable antibiotics, which also helps to significantly reduce the cost of using antibiotics.

On a hospital-wide scale, the two groups of antibiotics with the highest consumption are penicillin and cephalosporin. These are also the two groups of antibiotics most used in hospitals in Vietnam and some hospitals around the world due to their safety and popularity. Of the total 24 antibiotic active ingredients used in hospitals, the four active ingredients with the highest consumption rate in the entire hospital are: ampicillin + sulbactam; amoxicillin + clavulanic acid; cefaclor and cefuroxime. This result is different from some other studies. At Dien Bien Provincial General Hospital (2019), ceftriaxone was the antibiotic with the highest consumption level of 17.6 DDD/100 bed days [5]. With the Central Obstetrics Hospital being a specialized hospital for obstetrics and gynecology, the choice of antibiotics needs to ensure safety for pregnant women, so penicillin active ingredients combined with beta-lactamase inhibitors are given priority. This is similar to the results of the Obstetrics Department of Thai Nguyen A Hospital.

Analysis of trends of active ingredients used frequently in hospitals shows that the consumption of ampicillin/sulbactam tends to increase, while cefuroxime tends to decrease with statistical significance in the period 2019 - 2023. This result may be due to the supply situation of drugs in each stage at the hospital.

Analyzing the trend of antibiotic active ingredients that need priority management (group 1, group 2) according to Decision 5631/QD-BYT dated December 31, 2020, meropenem antibiotic tends to be consumed more from 2021. Compared to the carbapenem group, meropenem seems to have more evidence of safety in pregnant women than imipenem/cilastatin. According to the classification of drugs for pregnant women by the Australian Therapeutic Goods Administration (TGA), meropenem is classified as group B while imipenem is classified as group C. Studies worldwide also show that meropenem is preferred over imipenem/cilastatin because of its better activity against gram-negative bacteria, which is maximized by the ability to use higher doses due to lower neurotoxicity [7].

Conclusion

The study shows an overall picture of the situation of antibiotic use at the National Hospital of Obstetrics and Gynecology (NHOG) in the 5-year period of 2019 - 2023, in which the main points recorded are: Beta-lactam antibiotics are the main group of drugs used in the hospital (92.8%). The rate of use of original brand-name antibiotics (54.7%) and injectable antibiotics (91.4%) in the hospital is still relatively high. Antibiotics in the

priority antibiotic group have low consumption levels, however, meropenem antibiotics also tend to increase in the 5-year period. The two departments with the highest antibiotic use in the whole hospital are the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology and Infectious Diseases. Based on the research results, the hospital needs to strengthen the comprehensive antibiotic management program and evaluate the regular use of antibiotics.

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